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Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP6 Policy recommendations to enable Regulatory and HTA decision making

D6.5 Recommendations on policies to support the acceptance of heterogeneous health data research in regulatory and HTA decision-making (1)

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CONTENTS

D6.5 Recommendations on policies to support the acceptance of heterogeneous health data research in regulatory and HTA decision- making (1)	1
Document History	2
Executive Summary	5
Introduction	6
Building Consensus about what “Good Looks Like” in RWE Research	6
Real-World Evidence Research Process Map	7
Research Transparency to Establish Trust	9
Data Integrity and Governance Throughout the Study Process	10
Relevance and Scope of Recommendations	10
Relevance for Both HTA and Regulatory Decision-Making.....	10
Global Approach to Clinical Evidence.....	11
Report Audiences: Value for both Decision-Makers and Researchers.....	11
Organisation of Recommendations	12
Priority Levels within Sub-Recommendations.....	13
Next Steps: Planned Refinement and Expansion of the Recommendations	13
Policy Recommendations for Advancing RWE Acceptance	15
Recommendation 1: Research Transparency to Strengthen Trust in RWE	16
1.1 Define the Research Question and Study Design.....	18
1.2 Sharing Pre-Specified Study Protocols.....	19
1.3 Data Selection.....	23
1.4 Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) Development.....	24
1.5 Analysis and Interpretation of Evidence.....	26
1.6 Reporting and Dissemination of Results.....	28
Recommendation 2: Establishing the Fundamentals for Data Integrity and Governance	29
2.1 Data Characterisation.....	31
2.2 Data Extraction.....	32
2.3 Data Curation.....	33

Appendices	35
Abbreviations	35
Glossary	36
Current Tools and Approaches for Broader Adoption	39
Study Registration Platforms.....	44

Executive Summary

The IDERHA project has developed draft policy recommendations to support the acceptance and use of Real-World Data (RWD) and Real-World Evidence (RWE) in regulatory and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) decision-making for medicines and medical technologies. These recommendations aim to foster trust, transparency, and global alignment by promoting good research practices, data integrity, and governance. They are aimed at public decision-makers (regulatory authorities and HTA organisations) and researchers (industry, academia, clinical organisations) conducting studies for decision-making.

Traditional clinical trials remain essential but often lack generalisability and underrepresent diverse populations. RWE can complement trials by providing patient-centred insights, especially where randomised trials are unfeasible or unethical. Despite growing recognition of its value, concerns persist about robustness and evidentiary standards, and relevance in decision-making. The recommendations establish shared expectations for quality and conduct and focus on transparency and data provenance to demonstrate RWD quality and fitness for purpose.

IDERHA reviewed current regulatory and HTA policies, gathered expert feedback, and identified priority areas for alignment. The report introduces a generalised RWE study process map to ensure scientific rigor and guide organisations in developing or refining their policies, thereby strengthening confidence in the use of RWE for decision-making.

Key Recommendations for Conducting and Using RWE

- **Define and Align Research Questions Early:** Develop clear, relevant research questions aligned with regulatory and/or HTA needs.
- **Engage Decision-Makers Proactively:** Maintain dialogue with regulatory and HTA bodies throughout the study lifecycle.
- **Design Fit-for-Purpose Studies:** Tailor study design, data, and analyses to decision-making contexts.
- **Adopt Established Methodological Frameworks:** Use recognised guidelines (e.g. EMA, FDA, NICE, ICH) and register study protocols when appropriate.
- **Ensure Data Quality and Relevance:** Use reliable, relevant data sources with clear documentation of limitations and mitigation strategies.
- **Promote Transparency and Documentation:** Maintain comprehensive documentation of design decisions, deviations, analyses, and share results including uncertainty assessments.

Introduction

The goal of the IDERHA policy-focused activities is to accelerate the pace of policy development by building consensus recommendations on the use of RWD and RWE in regulatory and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) decision-making for medicines and medical technologies.

In 2024, [a landscape review](#) of the current policies from multiple regulatory authorities/bodies, HTA organisations and other relevant non-decision-making organisations was completed. The review was released for public consultation and targeted expert feedback was gathered through workshops and interviews. Based on this feedback, input from the IDERHA internal advisory boards, and findings from other similar literature in the field^{i,ii,iii,iv,v}, the IDERHA policy team decided to focus on the importance of demonstrating the rigor of RWE study conduct to counter the perception that RWE is of a lower scientific and evidentiary standard. To address these concerns, the first set of recommendations are focused on identifying and sharing a compilation of the current best practices for how to conduct and document rigorous RWE studies. By sharing this information, the goal is to build consensus across health care stakeholders about what robust RWE research looks like to help inform policy makers developing new RWD/RWE positions papers and guidance, as well as researchers seeking to conduct the studies.

Building Consensus about what “Good Looks Like” in RWE Research

There has been a marked increase in the number of policies and policy relevant programs on the use of RWE in the last decade. For many medical products, clinical studies remain critical to establishing safety and efficacy. However, traditional clinical studies have limitations which can limit generalisability and underrepresent diverse patient populations. In certain circumstances, such as ethical and/or recruitment challenges, no established standard of care in (very) rare disease and/or pathophysiological rationale, randomised clinical trials may not be feasible. Recognising these limitations underscores the need to complement traditional clinical evidence with RWE, enabling more inclusive, applicable, and patient-centred healthcare decisions and ultimately enhancing the real-world impact of medical research.

The health care ecosystem and stakeholders are increasingly advocating for more inclusive and diverse research to address gaps in the clinical evidence. The landscape review revealed that almost all the policy relevant documents acknowledged the potential for RWD and RWE to help close these gaps. However, many also raised concerns about the robustness of RWE study design and conduct, as well as questions about when, and to what extent, RWE could inform regulatory and HTA decision making. For more details, please refer to the [landscape review](#).

A fundamental challenge for RWE research is the absence of widely accepted standards equivalent to the “Good Clinical Practice” standards that exist for traditional clinical studies. Attempting to hold RWE studies to the same set of standards is neither practical nor appropriate, given the unique attributes of RWD. Trust in the scientific rigour of RWE research will continue to struggle without a shared set of expectations about the foundational best practices specific to studies using RWD.

Real-World Evidence Research Process Map

The team examined the information extracted in the landscape review to develop a simplified “process map” outlining the typical RWE research workflow. This map draws on and adapts the work of academic societies and other professional organisations such as [ISPOR and ISPE Joint Task Force](#), [Duke-Margolis Centre for Health Policy](#) and [NESTcc](#) amongst others. Please note that while this map is intended to signal a generalised process, additional steps may be needed for different types of studies (e.g. causal inference studies).

The proposed recommendations found later in this report are mapped to the different stages in the process. These initial policy recommendations seek to build on the work of early adopters and accelerate development by other countries and organisations who have not yet developed policies and guidance documents.

Recommendation 1:

Research Transparency to Strengthen Trust in RWE

Recommendation 2:

Establishing the Fundamentals for Data Integrity and Governance

Figure 1: General RWE Research Process map developed by IDERHA WP6.4.

Research Transparency to Establish Trust

As noted above, the first phase of recommendations focus on the key barrier to broader acceptance and adoption: the need for RWE-specific good research practices. Building on existing best practices, these recommendations emphasise the importance of establishing clear processes, robust mechanisms for documentation, and a shared set of expectations between researchers, sponsors and the end users of the results (e.g. regulatory authorities/bodies and HTA bodies). These measures are essential to ensure transparency and lay the foundation for trust.

Figure 2: Structure of research transparency recommendation and sub-recommendations

Data Integrity and Governance Throughout the Study Process

The analysis of regulatory documents on data collection reveals consensus on several key points. Generally, existing guidance aimed to ensure the reliability, validity, and integrity of data within clinical and regulatory settings.

- Emphasis on structured data characterisation as an initial step in determining the data quality relative to the study question
- Documentation of data provenance to ensure transparency from the data source, extraction and curation

Figure 3: Structure of data integrity and governance recommendation and sub-recommendations

Relevance and Scope of Recommendations

The following recommendations apply specifically to RWE studies intended for inclusion in submissions to regulatory authorities and/or HTA bodies to inform decision-making. RWE studies conducted for other purposes, such as product development, clinical trial design, or commercial market research are outside the scope of these recommendations.

Relevance for Both HTA and Regulatory Decision-Making

These recommendations are intended to apply to both regulatory and HTA policies and processes. While the types of research questions for medical product regulation and HTA submissions often differ, these recommendations focus on how studies are conducted

rather than the study questions themselves. Therefore, the principles of good research practice should remain the same regardless of the nature of the study question.

Global Approach to Clinical Evidence

These recommendations also aim to promote greater alignment across policy jurisdictions. The current lack of harmonisation in policies between different regions/countries limits access to critical clinical insights and hinders the ability to share important clinical evidence globally. Achieving greater global convergence would reduce uncertainty and inefficiencies in evidence generation, ultimately supporting more timely and equitable access to effective medicines and medical devices, and improve patient outcomes.

Report Audiences: Value for both Decision-Makers and Researchers

The key audiences for these recommendations are public decision-makers (i.e., medical product regulatory authorities and HTA bodies) and those conducting research that is intended to be used for decision-making (e.g. industry sponsors, academic and clinical research organisations). The recommendations seek to align expectations and best practices between those conducting the research and those making decisions based on the research.

Table 1: Overview of Potential Benefits to Key Audiences	
Groups conducting research for regulatory and HTA activities	Regulators and HTA bodies using research results for decision-making
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define and Align Research Questions Early: Allocate adequate time and resources to develop a study protocol with clearly defined research questions that are relevant to regulatory and/or HTA decision-making. Engage Decision-Makers Proactively and Iteratively: Plan for and invest in sustained engagement with regulatory and HTA authorities throughout the study lifecycle. This enhances alignment of methodological expectations, facilitates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Issue Clear and Transparent Guidance on RWE Acceptability: Provide examples of the specific types and sources of RWE that are acceptable or not acceptable for regulatory and/or HTA submissions. Clearly outline methodological standards, data quality expectations, and examples of contexts in which different RWE approaches may be considered valid. Enable Early Scientific Engagement on RWE Study Design: Allocate dedicated resources to support early and meaningful engagement with

timely feedback, and improves the overall credibility and relevance of the evidence.

- **Design Fit-for-Purpose Studies with Stakeholder Needs in Mind:**

Tailor study design, data selection, and analytical methods to address specific regulatory or HTA contexts. Consider the decision-makers' evidentiary standards, transparency requirements, and the level of uncertainty they are willing to accept.

- **Adopt and Follow Established Methodological Frameworks:**

Utilise recognised frameworks and guidelines (e.g. from EMA, FDA, NICE, CIHR, ICH E6/E8) to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and methodological rigor. Where appropriate, register relevant details of study protocols in advance.

- **Ensure Data Quality and Relevance:**

Use data sources that are fit for purpose (reliable and relevant). Clearly document data limitations, and how these are addressed in the analysis.

- **Promote Transparency and Documentation:**

Maintain comprehensive documentation of study design decisions, protocol deviations, and analytical choices. Share results and interpretations with external reviewers, including sensitivity analyses and uncertainty assessments, to facilitate robust decision making.

sponsors designing RWE studies. Early dialogue should focus on key aspects such as study objectives, design, data sources, endpoints, and analytical methods to ensure alignment with decision-making requirements.

- **Build Internal Capacity to Evaluate RWE Protocols:**

Ensure sufficient internal expertise and capacity to review and critically assess pre-specified RWE protocols. This includes the ability to evaluate scientific rigor, methodological appropriateness, and relevance of the study design to the intended regulatory or HTA purpose.

Organisation of Recommendations

The recommendations below are organised with an overarching and broad umbrella recommendation, followed by more detailed sub-recommendations associated with the steps in the research process map (Figure 1).

Priority Levels within Sub-Recommendations

To support the practical implementation of the recommendations, we have categorised them based on their **priority level**:

- **Essential:** Actions that are foundational and must be implemented to ensure credibility, transparency and acceptability of RWE studies. These are non-negotiable elements that directly impact the trustworthiness of the evidence.
- **Important:** Actions that significantly enhance the quality and robustness of RWE but may be adapted based on context, resources, or study objectives. While not mandatory, they are strongly encouraged.
- **Optional:** Actions that are beneficial and can add value, especially in specific contexts or for certain stakeholders. Their implementation may depend on available resources, study objectives, or stakeholder expectations.

This prioritisation of actions and considerations is intended to help stakeholders navigate the research process, allocate resources strategically and progressively strengthen practices in line with study goals and regional/local requirements across regulatory and HTA environments.

Next Steps: Planned Refinement and Expansion of the Recommendations

This is the first iteration of the report. As a core component of the project plan and IDERHA's commitment to public engagement and transparency, this report will be released for public consultation to seek input on the draft recommendations. Additionally, the team will convene a series of workshops with external experts and targeted discussions with key stakeholders to provide feedback. These activities are intended to: 1) solicit feedback on the recommendations, 2) collect additional information on other resources and information that should be considered for inclusion and 3) foster meaningful discussions and build consensus.

The team has identified several areas for future expansion of the recommendations which we explicitly solicit input on as part of the public consultation to be conducted in early 2026. Based on the feedback from the public consultation and consensus building workshops, the team will refine the content for a final report with policy recommendations, which will be issued in 2027.

Building from Existing Tools

As noted, several pilot programs ¹²³⁴⁵ have focused on advancing the understanding and use of RWD and RWE. These efforts have identified various “best-in-class” tools and programs to support broader adoption. Under the individual recommendations, we have developed an initial mapping of research and submission standards, tools and checklists to relevant components of the research process. This preliminary list is included in the Appendix [Current Tools and Approaches for Broader Adoption](#). This list was drawn from some of the policy documents reviewed in the original landscape analysis. We plan to solicit additional examples and assess all items to identify the current “best-in-class” resources.

Examples and Use Cases

As with most initiatives, examples of what has worked and what has not worked are critical for shaping future efforts. In the next phase of the recommendation development, the team plans to collect and consolidate information from pilot and implementation programs, including case studies, key lessons, and practical examples to create a shared resource.

Assessing the Need for Targeted Recommendations

During the recommendation development, IDERHA convened a series of workshops and targeted engagements with experts from different fields (e.g. regulatory and HTA) and product areas (e.g. medicines, medical devices including IVDs and AI/digital health products). Based on discussions in the workshops, it was determined that the first iteration of the recommendations should be broadly applicable for all relevant stakeholders. However, it was clear that there would be a need to identify areas where more specific recommendations for specific stakeholders would be appropriate. This will be a priority in the next phase of development.

For example, the landscape review identified notable differences in perspectives between medicines and medical devices.

¹ [MHRA Real-World Evidence Scientific Dialogue Programme - GOV.UK](#)

² [FDA Advancing RWE](#)

³ [National Evaluation System for Health Technology Coordinating Center \(NESTcc\) pilots](#)

⁴ [Japan/US bi-lateral initiative: Harmonization by Doing \(HBD\)](#)

⁵ European initiatives such as [EDHEN](#) or [DARWIN](#)

- For medicines, RWE was generally viewed as complementary or supplemental, providing insights into broader, more representative patient populations across varied clinical settings and capturing long-term safety and effectiveness beyond ideal trial conditions.
- For medical devices, there was a wider range of perspectives. Most documents reflected a similar, limited view of RWE as seen for medicines. However, at the other end of the spectrum, the US FDA guidance and supporting materials recognised the potential for RWE to serve as primary or even sole clinical evidence for a submission. This divergence may largely stem from the iterative nature of medical device development and innovation.

Policy Recommendations for Advancing RWE Acceptance

Based on the landscape review of current regulatory and HTA frameworks, expert stakeholder input, and cross-sector consensus discussions, the following 2 policy recommendations set out priority actions to strengthen the quality and transparency of RWE research and advance acceptance in regulatory and HTA decision-making for medicines and medical devices:

1. Research Transparency to Strengthen Trust in RWE
2. Establishing the Fundamentals for Data Integrity and Governance

Recommendation 1: Research Transparency to Strengthen Trust in RWE

Transparency throughout the research process is essential to build decision-makers' (i.e., regulatory authorities and HTA organisations) confidence in real-world evidence (RWE) studies and their results. Implementing and documenting concrete actions in key phases of the study will enable decision-makers to assess the reliability, reproducibility and validity of the findings.

RATIONALE: Trustworthiness in research is the degree of confidence decision-makers have in the credibility of the study's conduct and findings. Research transparency involves the disclosure of the research process from study design and data collection to analysis and findings. Transparency enables others to scrutinise and understand the entire research process, helping to establish trust in the findings.

The lack of consistent policies across stakeholders has led to confusion and misaligned expectations about transparency considerations that are appropriate for RWE studies compared to clinical trials. Almost all the documents in the landscape review included some guidance about the need for transparency in RWE studies. However, very few of them provided detailed information about which actions are expected to be taken and how the researchers could document them to create transparency. Many of the policies cited materials developed by external research societies such as ISPOR and ISPE as potential resources and tools.

DETAILS: We recommend researchers adopt transparency practices, at a minimum, in the following phases of the study.

<u>Define Research Question and Study Design</u>	<u>Sharing Pre-Specified Study Protocol</u>	<u>Data Selection</u>	<u>Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) Development</u>	<u>Analysis and Interpretation of Evidence</u>	<u>Reporting and Dissemination of Results</u>
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<p>Ensure RWE studies begin by setting clear and specific research questions, objectives and hypotheses, supported by relevant background literature.</p>	<p>Pre-specification and registration of RWE protocols is critical to establish transparency regarding the study and create accountability.</p>	<p>Ensure that real world data sources can be accurately identified and it can be established that they are suitable to answer the study question, i.e. fit for purpose.</p>	<p>Develop a pre-specified SAP and documenting any changes to it is essential for transparency and accountability.</p>	<p>Clear criteria for assessing study results to inform the interpretation creates consistency between and across research findings.</p>	<p>Clear practices for the dissemination and submission of RWE studies intended to support regulatory and/or HTA decision-making will build confidence in the findings.</p>
<p><u>Current tools/approaches to consider for broader adoption</u></p>					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PICO framework • NICE RWE Framework • HARPER 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENCePP Checklist and code of conduct • HARPER • STaRT-RWE checklist 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENCePP methodological guide • ROBINS-I • HARPER 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STROBE • RECORD-PE • CONSORT • CDA-AMC guidance

1.1 Define the Research Question and Study Design

Ensure RWE studies begin by setting clear and specific research questions, objectives and hypotheses, supported by relevant background literature.

RATIONALE: Setting a clear research question helps to establish a foundation for why and how the research study is taking place. It also encourages consideration of the type and nature of data required to answer a question, allowing due consideration as to whether RWE is the appropriate approach for answering the question, and whether suitable data are available. A structured research question also allows for greater study reproducibility.

DETAILS: The study development should include, as a minimum:

Essential

1. A clear and specific research question should be formulated at the start of a study, before study design or data sources are selected.
2. Primary and, where relevant, secondary study objectives should be set.
3. Consideration should be given as to whether RWE is appropriate to answer the chosen research question and achieve the objectives.
4. The research question should directly align with the intended use of the RWE i.e. where the results of the study are to inform healthcare decision-making e.g. an HTA or regulatory situation, it should be framed to answer the question relevant to that context
5. Consider if one research question is required, or whether several will be needed to get all the relevant information needed to inform the healthcare decision.
6. Structure research questions using a relevant framework such as PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcomes) framework or PICOT (including Timeframe).
7. Research questions should be included in study documentation as a descriptive study title including the study design, population and a version identifier if appropriate.
8. Justify why the study is taking place and how the research question and study objectives will address the well-defined problem or issue.
9. State what hypotheses are being tested. For studies aiming to test hypotheses around comparative effectiveness, having an explicit *a priori* hypotheses is recommended.
10. Consider the availability, quality and limitations of RWD sources. Ensure that local guidance is consulted to determine which sources of RWD are considered acceptable. If this is unclear from local guidance, contact the stakeholders for whom the expected RWE is being generated to discuss.

11. Do not retrofit research questions to data sources.
12. Choose a study design that is consistent with the research question.

Important

13. Conduct a critical review of the literature to assess what has previously been done to assess the research question being posed. Summarise applicable information from other studies and describe the extent to which these studies address the research question.
14. Engage early with relevant stakeholders to ensure the relevance of the research question and the applicability of its intended results. For example, engagement may include consultation with:
 - a. Regulators & HTA bodies to understand if the questions being explored are answering relevant questions and whether there are any additional considerations.

Optional

15. Adapt the PICO/PICOT framework as required to include the relevant elements, for example PECO to include exposure or PIRO for Diagnostic evidence (Population, Index Test; Reference Standard; Outcome)
16. Use an estimand framework when describing the rationale and appropriateness of outcome measures to be used.
17. Engage Patients/public to confirm relevancy of the question to their needs and experiences

1.2 Sharing Pre-Specified Study Protocols

Pre-specification and registration/sharing of RWE protocols is critical to establish the transparency of the research and create shared accountability.

RATIONALE: Pre-specification of study protocols is a critical step to enhancing the transparency, credibility and overall scientific rigor of the research. Policies that support opportunities to voluntarily and confidentially share study protocols with regulatory authorities and/or HTA bodies enhance compliant engagement and transparency. An additional step of [pre-registering key protocol](#) details could also support the credibility of the study results. As always, compliance with relevant regulatory requirements is required. The timing of disclosure of relevant study and result details should not prejudice the rights of the sponsor and study partners. Where premature disclosure of such details could harm the study and/or the rights of the sponsor an acceptable method of deferral and redaction of commercially confidential

information would sustain the scientific rigor of the research and protect the rights of the sponsor and study partners.

1. Protocol pre-specification advances quality and illustrates the rigor of RWE research.
2. Sharing details of the protocol (as outlined above) enhances transparency and builds trustworthiness:
 - a. Declaration of Intent: Registering study protocol details on a public platform before analysis begins publicly declares the study's intent and provides basic study information.
 - b. Allows stakeholders and decision-makers to understand the scientific thought process and agree on the study's approach.
 - c. Building Confidence: Registration of protocol details helps to build confidence among decision-makers.
3. Increase Methodological Credibility:
 - a. Prevents Data Manipulation: Finalising and publicly posting the study protocol details) *before* reviewing outcome data or performing analyses safeguards against selective analysis or elevating secondary questions to primary ones based on preliminary findings.
 - b. Prevents Publication Bias: Study registration helps reduce publication bias, as it allows identification of studies that might otherwise not be published (e.g. those with inconclusive or null results, or those that were only partially completed).
 - c. Promotes Accountability: Public registration encourages careful deliberation, planning and accountability from those conducting the study.

DETAILS: The pre-specified protocol should include, as a minimum:

Essential

1. **Research Question(s) and Objectives:** Clearly define the specific research question(s) and objectives, including whether the study is exploratory or hypothesis-evaluating (HETE). The research question should cover elements of the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome) scheme. Please see the recommendation on "[Define the Research Question and Study Design](#)" for additional details.
2. **Justification and Background:** Present the theoretical and scientific rationale for conducting the RWE study, including knowledge gaps it aims to address and its positioning (e.g. critical supporting evidence, auxiliary evidence, or exploratory objective).
3. **Study Design & Methodology**
 - a. **Study Design Type:** Clearly state the specific study design, such as observational cohort studies, pragmatic clinical trials (pRCTs), case-control,

nested case-control, or single-arm trials with external controls. A flow chart illustrating the implementation process is recommended.

b. **Target Population & Patient Selection:**

- i. Pre-specify the definition of the study population, including clear inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- ii. Describe the representativeness of the target population and any potential heterogeneity between the study population and the intended target population.
- iii. Detail the source of patient recruitment (e.g. clinical centres, registries) and the methods for identifying, selecting, including and retaining participants to minimise selection bias.
- iv. For external controls, justify the selection or exclusion of relevant data sources and ensure the choice aligns with the research question.

c. **Observation/Follow-up Period:** Reasonably define the study's observation period, follow-up period, start and end times, time intervals, and specific time points for observation or follow-up.

d. **Endpoints:** Clearly state the selection of effectiveness, efficacy and safety endpoints (primary, secondary, procedural, device, etc.), their definitions and measurement methods. If objective hard endpoints are difficult to apply, specific blinding measures might be needed.

e. **Control Group:** Describe the setting of the control group, including whether it's concurrent or historical. If matching-based methods are used, predetermined matching criteria should be included.

f. **Sample Size Estimation:** Include the determination of the sample size, ensuring it is adequate to answer the research question with sufficient statistical power.

4. **Data Management & Quality**

a. **Data Sources:** Describe the real-world data sources used (e.g. electronic medical records, claims data, registries, patient-generated data, device-generated data).

b. **Data Curation/Management Plan:** Specify the data curation and data management plan, including processes for collection, cleaning, processing, governance, storage system, record form and data security. It should ensure traceability of source data for key variables.

c. Address considerations for data quality, accuracy, completeness, provenance, reliability and relevance.

d. Detail auditing rules, methods and mitigation strategies to reduce errors.

5. **Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP):** The main analysis plan should be synchronously determined with the study protocol to avoid result-driven bias and guarantee transparency. It should clarify specific statistical methods, parameter settings and the rationale for their choice.

6. **Bias Minimisation and Control:** Describe methods for minimising and controlling potential biases (e.g. selection bias, information bias, confounding bias). This

includes justifying the handling of unknown or unmeasurable confounders and using sensitivity and quantitative bias analyses.

7. **Data Protection & Privacy:** Detail measures to protect patient privacy and ensure compliance with applicable data protection rules (e.g. GDPR).
 - a. **Informed Consent:** Describe how/if informed consent was needed and if so, how it was obtained. Provide the consent details (e.g. study purpose, duration, intended use of data, and access by third parties (monitors, auditors, regulatory authorities)).
8. **Protocol Amendment:** Any substantial changes to the protocol, data curation plan, or main analysis plan must be revised, dated, time-stamped, justified and communicated.

Important

1. **Data Governance:** Describe preliminary applicability evaluations of source or governed data (e.g. data governance, access, and use, including compliance with relevant laws and regulations).
2. **Ethics Committee Approval:** The acquisition and use of RWD for RWE must be reviewed by an ethics committee.

Optional

1. **Necessity and Feasibility:** Highlight why the research question is being addressed through RWE and the suitability of RWE to address the question.
2. **Past Use of RWD source(s):** Provide documentation of any previous fit-for-purpose assessments of the data source.
3. **Transparency of Evidence-Generating Process:** Address how the entire process of data collection and governance is transparent, clear and traceable. Measures include timely communication with evaluation agencies and disclosure of key protocol information.
4. **Early Communication:** Regulators encourage active communication on study plans and protocols before study implementation to ensure that consensus is reached on the use of RWE and the conduct of real-world studies. Compliance with any regulatory requirements for pre-submission of protocols and/or SAPs is required.

1.3 Data Selection

Ensure that real world data sources can be accurately identified and established that they are suitable to address the study question.

RATIONALE: Identification and description of data sources is critical to elaborate on the quality of the real-world data and conduct a preliminary applicability evaluation based on study objectives and design. This is the first step in establishing the data “reliability” and assessing the feasibility of the study. Please see the recommendation on [Establishing the Fundamentals for Data Integrity and Governance](#) for additional information.

DETAILS: The considerations for initial selection of data source(s) are, as a minimum:

Essential

1. The data must **represent the target population** of the of the product, considering the context of use, geographical and temporal coverage.
2. **Use metadata** for accurate identification and qualification of information, as it provides context about the data's purpose, generation, location, ownership, key variables and format. Metadata should be treated as data if changes to it would necessitate a revision of the generated evidence
3. **Conduct a preliminary applicability evaluation** of the data based on study objectives and design. Key information to be specified includes the data collection start and end times, data storage system and record form.
4. To address **prioritisation of data sources**, consider their **suitability**, which is assessed by **relevance** and **reliability**.
5. To address **relevance**, consider whether the data contains sufficient detail to capture needed information for the study question, its timeliness and generalisability.
 - a. This includes assessing coverage of critical variables like outcome, exposure/intervention, demographics, and important covariates.
 - b. It also involves understanding the care settings, geographical and temporal coverage and the representativeness of the data to the target population
6. Determine how closely the data, encompassing accuracy, completeness, provenance and traceability. This will address **reliability**.
 - a. Consider factors that influence reliability, such as, consistent and methodical data collection and processing, established data quality assurance and quality control policies, and documentation of data management practices, including transformation to Common Data Models (CDMs) and data cleaning.

7. Conduct **data quality checks** to identify errors, missing data, implausible values, and logical inconsistencies, with verification and remedial measures implemented.
 - a. The extent of missing data must be assessed and its potential impact examined, with predetermined thresholds for unacceptable levels of missingness
8. To ensure traceability of all variables back to the original source data, all aspects of data extraction, aggregation, curation, storage and availability for research should be planned and documented.

Important

1. If a single source of data is insufficient, **data linkage**, with supplemented sources may be necessary to obtain missing information and increase breadth and depth. The methodology for data linkage must be predefined, scientifically valid and protect privacy.

Optional

1. Registration of protocols may be dictated by regional/local laws or by the research institutions. For additional details, please see the recommendation on [Sharing Pre-Specified Study Protocol](#).

1.4 Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) Development

Develop a pre-specified SAP and documenting any changes to it, is essential for transparency and accountability.

RATIONALE: The study protocol outlines the overall research plan, including objectives, methodology and the data source(s). The statistical analysis plan (SAP) provides detailed specifications for how the data will be analysed. SAPs are often separate from the study protocol, though they can be included within it. Documenting the original SAP shows the study intentions and proposed methods, as well as prevents “data dredging.” Standard practice is to:

- SAP should be finalised in advance and before the analysis
- A sufficient description is expected to enable replication of analysis

DETAILS: The analysis plan should include, as a minimum:

Pre-specified analysis plan

Essential

1. Use of standardised framework such as PICOS (Population, Interventions, Comparators, Outcomes, Study design)
2. Where applicable, use an *estimand framework* to clearly define the treatment effect of interest, aligning the research question, population, endpoint and handling of intercurrent events
3. Inclusion of timelines and key milestones on expected deliverable
4. Inclusion of robust data governance frameworks (e.g. audit trails)
5. Pre-specification of all study design elements (e.g. index date), analysis (e.g. interim or final), conduct and reporting
6. Documentation of IRB/ethics committee approval or exemption
7. Documentation of human subject protections, including informed consent or waivers
8. Description of a clear data privacy plan (e.g. confidentiality terms, personal information safeguards, and data protection guarantees; compliance with legal and data governance frameworks)
9. Description of a change control process (e.g. planned deviations or amendments)
10. Inclusion of justification of analytical methods
11. Pre-specification of the primary, secondary and subgroup analyses, defining the objective for each
12. Pre-specification of potential sources of confounding and bias as well as methods that we will use to avoid them
13. Detailed data management and quality control procedures (e.g. strategies for handling missing data)

Important

1. Ethical and Methodological Considerations for Data Linking
2. Engagement of Stakeholders in the analysis plan design

Optional

1. Pre-registration (e.g. journal requirements for publication)
2. Use of standardised templates

Final analysis plan (outcome blinded)

Essential

1. The SAP should be finalised prior to conducting prespecified analyses and before reviewing outcome data.
2. Clear Reporting of Analytical Procedures (e.g. decision tree)
3. Procedures to mitigate potential sources of bias
4. Application of FAIR principles in data analysis
5. Description of data access and handling (e.g. who had access to the data, who conducted the analysis, and under what controls)

6. Inclusion of results from all planned and conducted analysis, with a clear statement

Optional

1. Documentation of Analytical Methodologies
2. Engagement in Collaborative Analyses Across Data Sources

1.5 Analysis and Interpretation of Evidence

Clear criteria for assessing the study results to inform the interpretation creates consistency between and across research findings.

RATIONALE: The increasing use of RWE in regulatory and HTA decision-making has highlighted the need for a structured and consistent approach to the interpretation of study findings. There is a lack of clear standards for real-world evidence research to assess whether results are coherent, robust methodological assumptions, or aligned with existing clinical and real-world evidence. This variability can undermine the reliability and credibility of RWE, especially its use in decision-making.

DETAILS: The analysis of the findings should include, as a minimum:

Essential

1. The consistency of results within the study should be evaluated, particularly across safety and effectiveness endpoints. Divergences between safety and effectiveness results should be explained, considering factors such as endpoint timing, outcome subjectivity, or potential biases.
2. Sensitivity analyses should be conducted to assess the robustness of the results to different model assumptions, analytical methods, and definitions. Areas to examine for variations include:
 - a. Operational definitions of exposures, outcomes, and covariates
 - b. Eligibility criteria and follow-up periods
 - c. Statistical model specifications
 - d. Approaches to handling missing data and outliers
 - e. Treatment switching and non-adherence
 - f. Quantitative bias analysis is also encouraged, particularly when assessing the potential influence of residual confounding, selection bias, and measurement bias. All sensitivity results must be transparently reported regardless of whether they support the primary analysis.
3. Subgroup analysis should be undertaken for key characteristics likely to influence treatment effect heterogeneity (e.g. age, sex, disease severity, site). Interaction

testing should be used to evaluate differences across subgroups. These factors should be pre-specified where possible.

4. Interpretation should be aligned with the primary research objectives and hypotheses, as defined in the protocol. The validity of conclusions should be assessed in the context of the statistical hypotheses and whether findings are consistent with what was anticipated. Deviations from hypotheses or analysis plans should be reported and explained.
5. Results should include information on the study's strengths and limitations. This includes discussion of study design, follow-up period, sample size and statistical power, outcome definitions, data source limitations, and risk of bias or residual confounding. The potential impact of each limitation on the interpretation of the findings should be clearly stated.

Important

1. The consistency of study findings with existing literature and evidence base should be assessed. This may include comparing findings with existing Investigator initiated studies, other RWE studies and RCTs. If consistent, the study may strengthen confidence in real-world generalisability. If inconsistent, researchers should explore and seek to explain potential causes.
2. Study results should be interpreted in relation to the intervention's mechanism of action or device technical features.
 - a. For medicines, this may include expected onset, duration of effect, and pharmacodynamics.
 - b. For devices, the analysis may include mechanical design, procedural elements, clinical care setting, clinician characteristics and physiological compatibility.
3. Interpretation should be informed by the type and quality of data used in the study.
 - a. This includes the relevance of the data to the research question, the reliability of variable measurement (e.g. outcome, exposure, confounders), and the completeness, accuracy, and traceability of the data.
 - b. Data quality issues such as inconsistent coding, implausible values, or missingness should be assessed for their impact on study conclusions.

Optional

1. More than one analytical approach may be used to assess the consistency and robustness of study results, where feasible. This may include comparing adjusted regression models with propensity score methods, or alternative causal inference frameworks. Divergences in findings should be explored, and convergence between methods strengthens validity.
2. The generalisability of study findings to the broader real-world target population and care setting should be discussed. This includes:
 - a. assessing the representativeness of the study population,
 - b. the relevance of the care context, and
 - c. the compatibility of outcomes with routine clinical practice.

3. Stakeholder perspectives, including clinicians, patients, or decision-makers, may inform the interpretation of results, especially where the findings are intended to support regulatory or HTA decisions.

1.6 Reporting and Dissemination of Results

Clear practices for the dissemination and submission of RWE studies intended to support regulatory and/or HTA decision-making will build confidence in the findings.

RATIONALE: Beyond structured reporting, how and where RWE findings are disseminated is important. Limited publication of results and variable submission formats reduces the transparency, comparability, and impact of RWE. Consistent dissemination expectations and practices build trust and improve utility across diverse audiences.

DETAILS: The framework should include, as a minimum:

Important

1. Encourage publication of results in peer-reviewed journals, preprints, or summary reports including lay summaries of peer-reviewed publications, where appropriate.
2. Where relevant, report how study results were shared with or communicated to patients, (but not targeting those whose data may have been used in the research) clinicians, and other non-regulatory stakeholders.
3. Align reporting with HTA and regulatory submission templates (e.g. tables, appendices, narrative summaries) to improve consistency and ease of review. Where submission is mandatory templates should be those provided by regulatory/HTA bodies.

Optional

1. Where possible and permissible, share metadata, and code lists as supplementary material in a public repository to improve transparency and reproducibility.
2. Provide plain language summaries of peer-reviewed publications of key findings for patients (but not targeting those whose data may have been used in the research) where appropriate.

Recommendation 2: Establishing the Fundamentals for Data Integrity and Governance

A standardised research framework that incorporates current best practices to document the assessment of the real-world data quality, and its fitness for purpose for regulatory and HTA decision-making. The recommendations are organised into three key elements (data extraction, data curation and data characterisation), with the relevant prioritisation for each level of recommendations and rationale included.

RATIONALE: As there is considerable variability in how data quality is assessed and documented across organisations, this recommendation aims to provide guidance for researchers and study sponsors stakeholders (including, researchers and study sponsors, regulators and HTA bodies) to establish a clear and standardised approach for data quality assessment and its documentation. 1. Standardising how data provenance is described and documented is one of the components needed to create greater transparency and reproducibility in research. This information would allow decision-makers to better understand and evaluate the dataset's context and applicability (fitness for purpose) for the study question and the analytical methods used. A unified framework can enable consistency and reliability in data curation, extraction and characterisation, and ensures that data is fit for purpose, useable and compliant for regulatory/HTA decision-making.

DETAILS: We recommend researchers adopt transparency practices, at a minimum, in the following phases of the study.

<u>Data Characterisation</u>	<u>Data Extraction</u>	<u>Data Curation</u>
Systematic and standardized approaches to evaluating and documenting the properties, quality, and limitations of data sources will enable assessment of representativeness to the target	Transparent and standardized approaches to retrieving relevant information and preparing data for analysis will demonstrate alignment with study objectives, reduce risks	Cleaning, standardizing, and organizing data to meet quality standards for analysis will strengthen the validity and reproducibility of results.

<p>population, period, and outcomes of interest, while identifying potential biases and constraints.</p>	<p>of bias, and ensure consistency and reliability.</p>	
<p><u>Current tools/approaches to consider for broader adoption</u></p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FDA RWE Elements Table • NICE RWE Framework – DATASAT tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMA Metadata Catalogue • ISPOR EHR Integration – Data Suitability Checklist 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FDA QA/QC Plan • CDA-AMC Reporting Recommendation Checklist

2.1 Data Characterisation

Systematic and standardized approaches to evaluating and documenting the properties, quality, and limitations of data sources will enable assessment of representativeness to the target population, period, and outcomes of interest, while identifying potential biases and constraints.

RATIONALE: Data sources for RWE can be heterogenous and may sometimes be not fit for purpose. Adequate data characterisations enable the evaluation of the dataset's representativeness to the target population, the time period and any outcomes of interest or relevance. Systematic and structured reporting of the dataset strengths, limitations and potential biases enhances its transparency and reliability.

Essential

1. Data Source Context:

- a. Document complete data source context, including:
 - i. Purpose of original data collection.
 - ii. Incentives or regulations that may affect data recording.
 - iii. Changes in data collection over time.

2. Fitness-for-Purpose Assessment

- a. Provide structured evaluation of:
 - i. Alignment between variables and endpoints.
 - ii. Target population representativeness.
 - iii. Endpoint validity in real-world context.
 - iv. Power/sample size adequacy for the research question.

3. Missing Data Analysis

- a. Conduct and document thorough missing data analysis, including:
 - i. Potential impacts of missing data and limitations on study conclusions.
 - ii. Sensitivity analyses using different missing data approaches.
 - iii. Transparent reporting of missingness by key variable and whether they invalidate research objectives.

Important

1. Representative Population Analysis

- a. Document population characteristics, including:
 - i. Demographic comparison to target population.
 - ii. Selection factors influencing data collection.
 - iii. Coverage of relevant subpopulations.
 - iv. Generalisability assessment

2. Variable Validity Assessment

- a. For key study variables, document:
 - i. Comparison to gold standard measures (if applicable).
 - ii. Validation studies (if available).
 - iii. Known measurement errors or biases.

- iv. Construct validity assessment (e.g. observed vs expected distributions).

Optional

1. Data Lineage Visualisation

- a. Provide visual representation of:
 - i. Data flows from source to analysis.
 - ii. Transformation and linkage processes.
 - iii. Quality check points.

Decision points in data processing

2.2 Data Extraction

Transparent and standardized approaches to retrieving relevant information and preparing data for analysis will demonstrate alignment with study objectives, reduce risks of bias, and ensure consistency and reliability.

RATIONALE: In RWE studies, transparent and well-documented extraction is essential to show how the data align with study objectives, ensure reproducibility, and minimises risks of bias. Inconsistent documentation of data extraction practices can undermine the credibility of findings and limit their use in decision-making.

DETAILS: The study documentation should include, as a minimum:

Essential

1. **Study Objective Alignment, (mainly researchers and study sponsors),** including:
 - a. Document how the extraction plan aligns with specific study objectives and research questions.
 - b. Demonstrate how extracted variables directly address the research question and study endpoints.
 - c. Identify and justify any indirect variables in relation to the research question.
2. **Dataset Documentation**
 - a. Record complete dataset provenance, including:
 - i. Dataset name and version.
 - ii. Data provider and extraction date.
 - iii. Timeframe covered (start/end dates).
3. **Data Transformation Documentation**
 - a. Document all data transformations, including:
 - i. Coding algorithms for derived variables.
 - ii. Natural language processing or AI methodologies used.
 - iii. Version control for extraction code/queries.

Important

1. Implement and document Quality Controls in the study documents, including:
 - a. Validation procedures for extraction tools.
 - b. Procedures for handling missing or inconsistent data.
 - c. Audit trails of extraction processes.

Optional

1. **Alternative Extraction Strategies**, including:
 - a. Document consideration of alternative extraction approaches.
 - b. Justify selection of final extraction methodology.
 - c. Report sensitivity analyses using alternative extraction methods.

2.3 Data Curation

Cleaning, standardizing, and organizing data to meet quality standards for analysis will strengthen the validity and reproducibility of results.

RATIONALE: Data curation steps are essential for maintaining data integrity and ensuring that study results are reproducible and reliable. Without systematic curation practices, issues such as missing values, coding inconsistencies, or undocumented transformations can compromise the validity of findings.

Essential

1. **Comprehensive Metadata Management**
 - a. Document complete metadata, including:
 - i. Standard terminologies used.
 - ii. Mapping to reference terminologies where applicable.
 - iii. Versioning of terminologies.
 - iv. Relationship between structured and unstructured data elements.
2. **Data Cleaning Protocols**
 - a. Document systematic cleaning procedures, including:
 - i. Outlier detection and handling methods.
 - ii. Missing data assessment and imputation strategies.
 - iii. Duplicate identification and resolution.
 - iv. Inconsistency detection and correction.
 - b. Provide rationale for all data modification decisions.
3. **Multi-source Data Harmonisation**
 - a. For studies combining multiple data sources, including:
 - i. Document variable harmonisation procedures.
 - ii. Map and validate common data elements across sources.
 - iii. Assess and document completeness of data mapping.
 - iv. Address temporal alignment issues between sources.

Important

1. **Data Quality Metric Reporting**
 - a. Implement and report standardised quality metrics:
 - i. Completeness (% of missing values by variable).
 - ii. Consistency (internal validation checks passed).

- iii. Plausibility (% of values within expected ranges).
- iv. Timeliness (lag between data collection and availability).

2. Issue Resolution Documentation

- a. Maintain structured documentation of:
 - i. Data quality issues identified.
 - ii. Methods used to address issues.
 - iii. Impact assessment of data quality problems.
 - iv. Unresolved limitations remaining after curation.

OPTIONAL: These elements represent best practices that further enhance data extraction transparency and trust. They may be useful for complex studies, novel data sources, or submissions where extraction methods may significantly impact results.

1. Curation Code Transparency

- a. Share with decision-makers the curation code or detailed workflows.
- b. Document software and versions used.
- c. Provide change logs for iterative curation processes.

Appendices

Abbreviations

CDA -AMC	Canada's Drug Agency - L'Agence des Medicaments du Canada
CDM	Common Data Model
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENCePP	European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology & Pharmacovigilance
EUNetHTA	European Network for Health Technology Assessment (Europe)
FDA	U.S. Food and Drug Administration
HAs	Health Authorities
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HMA	Heads of Medicines Agencies
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
ICH	International Council for Harmonisation
IDAGC	Integrated Data Access Governance Council
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative (Europe)
IQWiG	Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (Germany)
ISPE	International Society for Pharmacoepidemiology
ISPOR	International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (England)
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PBAC	Pharmaceutical Benefits Advisory Committee
PICO	Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome
PMA	Premarket Approval
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
REALISE	Real World Data in Asia for Health Technology Assessment in Reimbursement
ROBINS-I	Risk Of Bias in Non-randomised Studies - of Interventions
RWD	Real World Data
RWE	Real World Evidence
WP	Work Package
ZIN	National Health Care Institute (Netherlands)

Glossary

Bias-Minimisation Techniques

Methods employed to control for potential confounders and biases, reducing systematic errors that could distort study results.

Conceptual Definitions

High-level, theoretical descriptions of variables, describing what they represent or signify within the context of the research.

Data Characterisation

The evaluation and documentation of the properties, quality, and limitations of curated data. Data characterisation, or metadata, aims to identify the strengths and weaknesses of original data sources, covering aspects such as the purpose of data collection, site types, data types (e.g. administrative claims, clinical notes), and patient demographics. This information is critical for evaluating data suitability for study questions, supporting study protocol development, and contributing to findings' relevance and reliability assessments.

Data Completeness

The extent to which all necessary data points are collected and available for analysis. This can include various considerations for key study variables, including the study population (inclusion/exclusion criteria), exposures, outcomes, and covariates.

Data Curation

The process of cleaning, standardising, and organising data to meet quality standards necessary for analysis. This includes data cleaning, transformation, and harmonisation to ensure it meets quality standards for analysis. Curation may also involve the annotation and integration of data from diverse sources to make them usable for specific research or decision-making processes. These components play a central part in establishing the provenance of the RWD and ensuring that it has not been mismanaged.

Data Extraction

The process of retrieving relevant information from collected data sources and preparing it for analysis.

Data Linkage Methodology

Predefined procedures for connecting datasets, including matching criteria and privacy protections, to ensure valid integration of multiple data sources.

Data Provenance

Documentation of the origin, processing history, and transformations applied to data, establishing its traceability and reliability throughout the research lifecycle.

Data Privacy and Confidentiality

Protection of individuals' personal and sensitive information within datasets, ensuring compliance with legal regulations such as GDPR and maintaining participant trust.

Data Quality Assurance

Systematic measures to ensure accuracy, completeness, consistency, and reliability of data throughout the research process, including validation, auditing, and quality control procedures.

Data Quality Checks

Procedures used to identify and address errors, inconsistencies, missing data, or implausible values within datasets, ensuring data integrity and validity.

Data Sharing & Transparency

Public or controlled access to datasets and protocols, allowing others to verify and reuse findings, thus enhancing credibility and reproducibility.

Data Security

Protocols and technological measures in place to safeguard data against unauthorised access, loss, or breaches.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

A European Union data protection law that took effect in 2018. Its purpose is to give individuals more control over their personal data by setting strict standards for how organisations collect, process, and protect it. It applies to any organisation that handles the data of EU residents, regardless of where the company is based.

Good Clinical Practice (GCP)

GCP is an international ethical and scientific quality standard for clinical trials involving human subjects. It ensures that the rights, safety, and well-being of trial participants are protected and that the data from clinical trials is credible and reliable. GCP provides a framework for all stages of a clinical trial, including its design, conduct, recording, and reporting.

Informed Consent

A process through which study participants are adequately informed of the research purpose, procedures, risks, and rights before agreeing to participate, ensuring ethical standards.

Operational Definitions

Precise, measurable descriptions (of variables) to ensure consistency and reproducibility across different researchers and sites

Reproducibility

The ability for independent researchers to replicate study results using the same data, methods, and procedures, confirming the reliability of findings.

Research Transparency

The open and complete disclosure of all aspects of the research process, from initial conception and protocol design to data collection, analysis, and dissemination, enabling verification and critique.

Research Lifecycle

The entire sequence of stages in a research project where transparency practices should be applied to ensure trust, reproducibility, and credibility, including planning, conducting, analysing, documenting, and dissemination.

RWD (Real World Data)

Information pertaining to health status and health care delivery that is collected routinely from sources other than traditional clinical trials. RWD includes data generated in real-world settings, such as electronic health records, claims databases, patient registries, and wearable device data.

RWE (Real World Evidence)

Evidence derived from the analysis of RWD regarding the usage, effectiveness, and potential benefits or risks of an intervention. RWE provides insights to support regulatory decisions, health policy, and clinical practice.

Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP)

A comprehensive plan authored prior to data analysis that specifies the statistical

methods, models, and procedures, ensuring transparency and reproducibility of the analytic process.

Target Population

The specific group of individuals or entities the research is designed to characterise or generalise its findings to, based on shared characteristics and criteria.

Current Tools and Approaches for Broader Adoption

Tools or approaches	Relevance	Cited by
<u>ADVANCE Code of Conduct for vaccines</u>	<p>Includes 45 recommendations in 10 topics (incl. transparency, conflicts of interest, study protocol and report). Each topic includes a definition, a set of recommendations and a list of additional reading. The concept of the study team is introduced as a key component of the ADVANCE Code of Conduct with a core set of roles and responsibilities for involved stakeholders.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sets principles for independence and transparency in vaccine observational studies - Establishes ethical and scientific principles for independently run vaccine studies <p>Requires disclosure of funding, data access rules, and governance</p>	
<u>CDAAMC Guidance for Reporting RWE</u>	<p>Comprehensive and fit for purpose reporting guidance - set of common principles and core standards to optimise the utility and transparency of RWE to both HTA and regulatory bodies. Particularly relevant to conduct an end-to-end RWE study</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aims at standardised RWE reporting for clinical practice - Standardises how RWE is reported, promoting comparability and reducing selective reporting - Emphasises clarity in defining populations, endpoints, and data provenance 	
<u>CONSORT Statement</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides a structured way to report trials, including pragmatic and hybrid RCT-RWE designs - Makes it easier to assess risk of bias and generalisability. 	<p>EMA NICE FDA</p>
<u>EMA metadata and reporting standards</u>	<p>Developed to provide regulators, researchers (including academia and pharmaceutical industry) and other interested stakeholders with</p>	<p>EMA</p>

	<p>recommendations on the use of the catalogues from the perspective of the data user. Specifically, the guide focuses on describing the steps and best practices on identifying a suitable data source, when planning a study.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defines minimal reporting requirements for submissions and public registries - Ensures structured capture of RWE study metadata for regulatory submission - Facilitates traceability and replication of findings 	
<p><u>ENCePP Code of conduct and checklist for Study Protocols</u></p>	<p>Encourages reflection on key principles during the design and drafting of a pharmaco-epidemiological or pharmacovigilance study protocols. The Checklist is practical and aims to enhance the quality of these studies rather than to standardise them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensures completeness, methodological rigor, and transparency in protocol writing - Guarantees completeness in protocol design before the study starts - Prevents retrospective protocol changes (reducing p-hacking or selective analysis) 	<p>EMA NICE HAS</p>
<p><u>ENCePP Guide on Methodological Standards in Pharmacoepidemiology</u></p>	<p>Harmonises best practices in RWD study methods and provides a common reference for methods (e.g. confounding control, data linkage, causal inference).</p>	<p>EMA NICE HAS</p>
<p><u>Good Pharmacovigilance Practices Module VIII (EMA)</u></p>	<p>Guidelines on both interventional and non-interventional PASS, with a primary focus on non-interventional ones. Comprehensive framework for the management of Risk Minimisation Measures (RMMs) to ensure that safety risks are effectively communicated and mitigated throughout the product lifecycle, improving patient safety and regulatory compliance.</p>	<p>EMA</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applies rigorous safety monitoring standards to post-authorisation studies - Mandates protocols, data sources, and analytic plans in PASS submissions 	
<u>ISPOR/ISPE RWE Recommendations (Joint Task Force)</u>	<p>Provide a standardised and transparent framework for generating, analysing, and RWE to support more informed decision-making in healthcare, drug development, and regulatory processes. It fosters consistency and quality across RWE research, which is crucial for integrating real-world data into clinical and policy decisions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Useful for designing comparative effectiveness studies using RWD - Encourages detailed documentation of study assumptions and methods 	FDA
<u>HAS Realworld studies guidance</u>	<p>Provide guidance on conducting and evaluating RWE studies to ensure their scientific rigor, relevance, and value in healthcare decision-making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarifies how RWE will be evaluated for reimbursement decisions - Has a section on developing RWE questions 	HAS
<u>HARPER Protocol Template</u>	<p>Structure framework designed to facilitate the development of comprehensive and clear research protocols (pharmacovigilance and pharmacoepidemiology studies).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardised template promoting reproducible RWE study designs - Drives consistency and completeness in planning of RWE studies - Includes detailed rationale, bias mitigation strategies, and operational planning 	EMA NICE
<u>NICE RWE framework</u>	<p>Guidance to ensure that the generation and application of RWE are scientifically robust, transparent, and relevant for healthcare</p>	NICE

	<p>decision-making. It is designed to support stakeholders, including regulators, payers, clinicians, and researchers, in systematically producing and evaluating RWE.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lays out clear expectations for acceptable RWE in regulatory/HTA submissions - Promotes public registration, protocol sharing, and clarity on data provenance 	
<u>PICO framework</u>	<p>Simple and powerful tool used to formulate clear, focused clinical questions, especially useful in evidence-based practice. It breaks down complex questions into manageable components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standard question framework improves clarity of intent in research - Makes comparator selection and outcome justification explicit 	NICE CDA-AMC IQWIG
<u>RECORD-PE</u>	<p>Set of guidelines designed to enhance transparency, quality, and reproducibility in pharmaco-epidemiological research relying on routinely collected health data, such as electronic health records, claims data, or registries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhances transparency in database and registry studies. - Encourages detailed reporting on data linkage, population definitions, and missing data 	EMA NICE HAS CDA-AMC
<u>ROBINS-I</u>	<p>Relevant to assess the risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. It helps determine the credibility of study findings by systematically evaluating the potential biases across multiple domains.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides structured bias assessment in non-randomised studies - Identifies potential confounding, selection bias, or measurement issues 	NICE FDA CDA-AMC IQWIG

<p><u>STaRT-RWE Checklist</u></p>	<p>Comprehensive framework to design, conduct, and report Real-World Evidence (RWE) studies with clarity, transparency, and consistency.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensures consistent planning and documentation of implementation studies - Reduces ambiguity in study intent and reduces selective reporting 	<p>EMA NICE</p>
<p><u>STROBE</u></p>	<p>Checklist aimed at improving the transparency, completeness, and quality of reporting observational research - including cohort, case-control, and cross-sectional studies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardises reporting structure, enabling reviewers to assess validity 	<p>CDA-AMC IQWiG EMA HAS</p>
<p><u>Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use</u></p>	<p>Legislation underpinning Good Pharmacovigilance Practices Module VIII</p>	<p>EMA</p>

Study Registration Platforms

ClinicalTrials.gov

This is a widely recognised registry primarily designed for Randomised Controlled Trials (RCTs). However, it can also accommodate observational studies, though the process might be cumbersome. It is operated by the National Institutes of Health's National Library of Medicine. Registration on ClinicalTrials.gov is recommended before enrolling the first patient for trials, with no exceptions. It allows for the storage of study protocols and analysis plans for all study types. This platform helps prevent selective analysis and reporting of endpoints.

HMA-EMA Catalogues of real-world data sources and studies

Hosted by the European Medicines Agency this register focuses on non-interventional post-authorisation studies, both prospective and retrospective. Registration of relevant studies should be undertaken in compliance with legislation.

The Open Science Framework (OSF)

This platform provides pre-registration services for observational studies and is encouraged to publish study protocols and analysis plans.

International Clinical Trials Registration Platform / World Health Organisation (ICTRP/WHO)

This is a global platform for clinical trial registration.

ISRCTN registry (International Standard Randomised Controlled Trial Number)

This registry actively promotes the use of Core Outcome Sets (COS) and engagement with the COMET database.

PROSPERO portal

This is registry specifically for systematic reviews and meta-analyses.

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